

STATE OF ORGANIZATION OF COOPERATION IN THE PREVENTION OF HARASSMENT AND VIOLENCE AGAINST CHILDREN

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Abstract: This article provides a comprehensive analysis of the state of cooperation in preventing harassment and violence against children in our country. It also presents the opinions of scholars, the interaction between entities, problems arising in cooperation, and proposals and recommendations for their solutions. The article discusses strengthening interaction between entities involved in protecting children from all forms of violence and the public.

Keywords: violence against children, prevention of harassment and violence, cooperation mechanisms, prevention inspectors, information exchange, practical cooperation, "Child Safety" platform, public participation, protection order.

In society, cooperation by law enforcement agencies in the fight against and prevention of each offense is of great importance. Therefore, cooperation in the prevention of harassment and violence against children is also relevant in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Cooperation is one of the most effective ways to ensure the prevention of offenses, in which the necessary forces and means are concentrated and directed towards a single (common) goal - to eliminate the causes of offenses and the conditions contributing to them. This, in turn, serves to increase the effectiveness of crime prevention activities.

The adoption of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP 256 "On Approving the Strategy for the Protection of Children from All Forms of Violence for 2026-2030" has led to the adoption of a strategy aimed at creating an atmosphere of intolerance towards all forms of violence against children in society, reliable protection of their rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests[1]. The definition of priority tasks in this strategy, aimed at coordinating activities in the field of combating crime and preventing offenses, strengthening the role of civic position in society in terms of respect for the law, and an uncompromising attitude towards cases of offenses, creates the need to take measures to increase the effectiveness of cooperation in preventive activities with persons who have committed violence against children.

No state body, without interaction with other structures, can ensure the effectiveness of its activities only within its internal capabilities[2]. Subjects of crime prevention interact with sectoral services, other law enforcement agencies, state and public organizations that are part of the system in the implementation of the tasks assigned to them.[3].

In legal literature, one can observe scientific definitions of cooperation in the field of crime prevention, differing in content, forms, and methods.

Legal scholar V.A. Afanasyev defines cooperation in the field of crime prevention as the effective use of forms and methods of activity, official powers by subjects engaged in this activity in mutual agreement[4], while J.S. Mukhtorov defines it as the joint activity of subjects

in an agreed manner based on a regular analysis of the criminogenic situation in the administrative territory [5].

Professor M.Z. Ziyodullayev, approaching the concept of cooperation from the point of view of cooperation based on the support points of internal affairs bodies, believes that it is necessary to divide it into the following three groups: 1) cooperation between sectoral services of internal affairs bodies; 2) interaction between the sectoral services of internal affairs bodies and other bodies and institutions of state power; 3) cooperation between the sectoral services of the internal affairs bodies and public structures [6].

Professor I. Ismailov, in his research, conditionally divides cooperation in the system of combating crime into four areas: a) internal departmental cooperation; b) interdepartmental cooperation; c) public relations; d) international cooperation [7].

When discussing the forms of cooperation, legal scholars N.D. Nechevina, I.P. Yablokov, A.D. Polishuk, and V.K. Kolpakov distinguish such forms of cooperation as: exchange of information; joint distribution of forces and resources in accordance with the operational situation; joint planning and determination of measures; joint study and analysis of the criminogenic situation; conducting joint activities; joint implementation of legal advocacy; mutual exchange of experience; training citizens in cooperation [8].

Professor M.Z. Ziyodullayev, on the other hand, analyzed the cooperation organized on the basis of the support points of the internal affairs bodies, conditionally dividing it into two main forms: a) mutual exchange of information; b) practical cooperation, manifested in the joint planning, implementation, summarization of the results of activities, mutual assistance and support in the performance of certain tasks" [9].

In general, it can be observed that the above classifications are carried out taking into account specific aspects in the field of crime prevention: the scope of authority of the subjects of cooperation, the scale and share of cooperation. We consider it necessary to study the cooperation of internal affairs bodies (crime prevention units) in the field of preventive activities with persons who have committed child abuse, dividing it into the following three main groups:

- 1) *cooperation between sectoral services of internal affairs bodies (internal cooperation);*
- 2) *interaction (external cooperation) between the sectoral services of internal affairs bodies and other bodies and institutions of state power;*
- 3) *cooperation between the sectoral services of internal affairs bodies and public structures (external cooperation).*

Based on these analyses, the cooperation of internal affairs bodies in the process of organizing preventive activities with subjects carrying out the prevention of harassment and violence against children can be divided into the following two forms:

- 1) *Cooperation in the form of information exchange, providing for the mutual provision of information on harassment and abuse of children ;*
- 2) *Cooperation in a practical form, providing for the application of individual educational and preventive measures aimed at preventing the commission of harassment and violence against children .*

Today, both forms of cooperation differ in their specific characteristics and significance. In the course of a survey conducted among employees of internal affairs bodies, when specialists were asked the question: "*Which form of interaction of internal affairs bodies with other subjects, in your opinion, is more important and effective in preventing harassment and*

violence against children?," 53% of participants answered that it is cooperation in a practical form, and another 47% noted that it is cooperation in the form of information exchange.

Also, when the participants of the sociological survey were asked the question "*Which subjects, in your opinion, are most important for the internal affairs bodies to cooperate with in preventing harassment and violence against children?*," 47.2% of respondents believed that it is with citizens' self-government bodies, 19.4% - with employment assistance centers, 15.1% - with local authorities, 13.3% - with healthcare bodies (medical institutions), 3.6% - with judicial bodies, 1.3% - with prosecution bodies, and 0.4% - with other subjects.

The most common form of cooperation is the exchange of information. Because timely, regular, and prompt reliable information allows for optimal decision-making on the situation[10].

According to the Russian scientist P.N. Astapenko, the essence of the implemented changes is the gradual transformation of the police from a law enforcement agency into a public-oriented body and a professional service providing services in the field of ensuring public order and security. Believes that the active implementation of the concept called "Collective Police" will lead to cooperation between the police, society, and the [population](#). [1]

Another Russian scholar, I.T. Tarasov, wrote: "A single government cannot satisfactorily perform all the tasks it has undertaken without the participation of public bodies" [2]. Agreeing with this view, the effective use of the power of community representatives will be effective in combating child abuse.

Internal affairs bodies (prevention inspectors) cooperate within their competence with entities cooperating in the exchange of information.

In particular, it cooperates with the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the development and approval of state programs and strategies in the field of protecting children from all forms of violence, submitting proposals.

In particular, from the enterprise, institution, and organization where the person who has committed harassment and violence against children works, they can receive information about their attitude to work, interaction with employees working together, behavior, wages, etc., from the mahalla law enforcement station - information about the family situation and socio-physiological characteristics of interaction with fellow citizens of persons who have committed or may commit harassment and violence against children, from medical institutions - information about their health, drug addiction, or chronic alcoholism, and, in turn, the internal affairs bodies, by submitting a recommendation to the mahalla law enforcement station to assist in assigning social benefits to the person who has committed harassment and violence against children, can provide information about their social status, administrative procedural documents on the commission of an administrative offense by the person who has committed harassment and violence against children, as well as information about their antisocial behavior. Through this, cooperation with authorized entities is carried out.

Also, when the Authorized Person of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the Rights of the Child (Children's Ombudsman) makes a decision with the internal affairs bodies on initiating a criminal case or refusing to initiate a criminal case in the event of receiving information about crimes against the life, health or sexual freedom of children, including sexual intercourse with a person under the age of sixteen or unnatural satisfaction of sexual needs or indecent acts against him, involving a minor as an executor of acts of a pornographic nature,

pimping with the involvement of a minor, organizing brothels, he notifies the Authorized Person for the Rights of the Child in writing within three days.

Cooperation with the National Commission on Children's Issues of Internal Affairs bodies will be carried out to form immunity against offenses in children, analyze the state of work carried out among them to prevent offenses, neglect, and antisocial behavior, as well as the exploitation of children, violence against them, and ensure their rehabilitation, and take measures to increase their effectiveness.

Article 10 of the Law "On the Protection of Children from All Forms of Violence" defines the powers of the National Commission on Children's Issues in the field of protecting children from all forms of violence.

National Commission on Children's Issues:

- coordinates the activities of state bodies and organizations carrying out activities to protect children from all forms of violence in the field of protecting the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of children, including the activities of the commissions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions, the city of Tashkent and districts (cities) on children's issues;

- develops and adopts short-term and long-term programs aimed at preventing and eliminating all forms of violence against children;

- organizes the provision of the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of children, their healthy lifestyle;

- contributes to the physical, intellectual, spiritual, and moral development of children;

- takes measures to prevent children from being deprived of parental care, as well as to prevent neglect and homelessness among children;

- organizes the development and implementation of state and other programs in the field of prevention of neglect and delinquency among children, as well as control over their implementation;

- assesses, monitors, and increases the effectiveness of measures taken to protect the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of children;

- identifies and analyzes the causes and conditions for the emergence of systemic shortcomings and takes measures to eliminate them by improving law enforcement practice and legislation;

- carries out the collection, storage, processing, analysis, as well as use of data on violence against children.

Prevention inspectors of internal affairs bodies interact with commissions on children's issues on the protection of children from harassment and violence within the framework of the above-mentioned powers.

In addition, offenses committed by children who have committed harassment and violence against children will also be sent to the National Children's Commissions for consideration.

The National Agency for Social Protection under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the working body of the National Commission on Children's Issues[3].

Internal affairs bodies will cooperate with the National Agency for Social Protection under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in developing programs to prevent violence against children and protecting the rights and interests of children in need of social protection.

Internal affairs bodies cooperate with the National Agency for Social Protection under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Agency is the authorized state body in the field of protecting children from all forms of violence. Authorized state body:

- develops and implements programs and measures to prevent all forms of violence against children, protect children affected by violence, as well as children at risk of violence against them;

- develops procedures and standards aimed at the timely detection of all forms of violence against children, reporting them, and taking measures to respond to them, and also coordinates their implementation;

- together with the subjects carrying out activities to protect children from all forms of violence, assesses the life situation of children affected by violence and children at risk of violence against them, determines the level of risk of violence, develops a child protection plan and coordinates its implementation;

- organizes the provision of medical, social, psychological, legal, and other necessary services to children affected by violence, resolves issues of ensuring their rights and legitimate interests without separating them from their family, including close relatives;

- organizes the protection of the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of children at risk of violence against them;

- takes measures to develop social services aimed at strengthening families, increasing the skills and responsibility of parents (persons replacing them) in fulfilling their obligations in order to prevent the separation of children from their families;

- takes measures to develop family forms of alternative care and placement for children left without parental care;

- organizes a system of support for women in difficult life situations, single fathers or mothers, and families with young children;

- sends children affected by violence for rehabilitation;

- participates in monitoring the implementation of international standards in the field of children's rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests into legislation and compliance with child rights legislation in the activities of state bodies and other organizations;

- collects, stores, processes, analyzes, and uses information about children affected by violence, as well as about children at risk of violence against them;

- cooperation with government bodies, citizens' self-government bodies, non-governmental non-profit organizations, and other civil society institutions that carry out or participate in activities related to the protection of children from all forms of [violence](#)[4].

Internal affairs bodies cooperate with the prosecutor's office, and according to Article 12 of the Law "On the Protection of Children from All Forms of Violence," the powers of the prosecutor's office to prevent violence against children are defined.

- participates in the development and implementation of state programs, territorial programs, and draft regulatory legal acts in the field of protecting children from all forms of violence;

- monitors the implementation of legislation on the protection of children from all forms of violence;

- takes measures to protect the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of the victim of violence;

develops proposals for improving legislation on the protection of children from all forms of violence;

cooperates with government bodies, citizens' self-government bodies, non-governmental non-profit organizations, and other civil society institutions that carry out or participate in activities related to the protection of children from all forms of violence[5].

Article 13 of the Law "On the Protection of Children from All Forms of Violence" defines the powers of internal affairs bodies to prevent harassment and violence against children in the field of protecting children from all forms of violence. Including:

participates in the development and implementation of state programs, territorial programs, and drafts of regulatory legal acts in the field of protecting children from all forms of violence;

develops proposals for improving legislation on the protection of children from all forms of violence;

takes measures to protect the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of children, identifies the causes of their violations;

conducts a systematic analysis of the causes and conditions contributing to the commission of crimes and violence among children;

participates in the identification of children at risk of violence against them;

receives, registers, and verifies information on the facts of violence against children, conducts inquiries and preliminary investigations on them;

identifies and keeps records of persons involving children in committing offenses or other antisocial acts or committing other unlawful acts against children, as well as parents or persons replacing them who evade fulfilling their obligations or improperly fulfill their obligations to support, educate, and raise children, or negatively affect their behavior or treat them cruelly;

takes urgent measures for the immediate prevention and suppression of violence against children;

assists the authorized state body in identifying children left without parental care, in the withdrawal of the child from the parents (one of them) in cases of an immediate threat to the life or health of the child, as well as in determining their place of temporary stay;

sends information about parents who have committed child abuse and neglect to the authorized state body;

takes measures provided for by international treaties of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the protection of children from all forms of violence;

carries out the collection, storage, processing, analysis, and use of information about persons who have committed or are prone to committing violence against children;

cooperates with government bodies, citizens' self-government bodies, non-governmental non-profit organizations, and other civil society institutions that carry out or participate in activities related to the protection of children from all forms of [violence](#)[6].

Internal affairs bodies interact with the bodies of the National Guard of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and according to Article 14 of the law, they have the authority to protect children from all forms of violence. National Guard of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

participates in the development and implementation of state programs, territorial programs, and draft regulatory legal acts in the field of protecting children from all forms of violence;

develops proposals for improving legislation on the protection of children from all forms of violence;

participates, within its competence, in the implementation of measures for the prevention of offenses, including in the field of protecting children from all forms of violence, identifies the causes of these offenses and the conditions contributing to them, and takes measures to eliminate them;

§ is defined as "cooperates with state bodies, citizens' self-government bodies, non-governmental non-profit organizations, and other civil society institutions that carry out or participate in activities related to the protection of children from all forms of violence." [7].

Prevention inspectors of internal affairs bodies cooperate with the Committee for Family and Women of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and according to Article 15 of the law, their powers in the field of protecting children from all forms of violence are defined. Committee for Family and Women:

takes measures to identify and eliminate the causes and conditions that allow children to find themselves in situations requiring protection from violence, and to prevent the occurrence of such situations;

informs state bodies and organizations carrying out activities to protect children from all forms of violence about children who are victims of violence and children at risk of violence against them;

participates in the assessment of the life situation of children affected by violence and children at risk of violence against them, as well as their family situation;

participates in the development and implementation of a plan for the protection of a child who has suffered from violence, as well as a child at risk of violence against him;

ensures the protection of the rights and legitimate interests of girls, enhances their role and activity in the socio-political life of the country, and guarantees gender equality;

implementation of targeted measures to promote a healthy lifestyle among families, strengthening spiritual and moral values in the [family](#)[8].

Internal affairs bodies cooperate with the Youth Affairs Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and according to Article 16 of the law, their powers in the field of protecting children from all forms of violence are defined. Youth Affairs Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

participates in the implementation of measures to organize the social and legal protection of orphaned children and children left without parental care aged fourteen to eighteen years, who need social protection, as well as measures for the social rehabilitation and social adaptation of victims of offenses, persons prone to committing offenses, who have committed offenses, including those previously convicted and released from places of deprivation of liberty, aged fourteen to eighteen years;

participates in the development and implementation of a plan for the protection of a child who has suffered from violence, as well as a child at risk of violence against him;

participates in the implementation of measures aimed at protecting the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of young people aged fourteen to eighteen, preventing offenses and crimes among them, including the prevention of all forms of violence against children;

cooperates with government bodies, citizens' self-government bodies, non-governmental non-profit organizations, and other civil society institutions that carry out or participate in

activities related to the protection of children aged fourteen to eighteen from all forms of [violence](#).^[1]

Internal affairs bodies cooperate with government bodies and educational institutions, non-governmental educational organizations in the field of education, and Article 17 of the law defines the following powers in the field of protecting children from all forms of violence:

- develops and participates in the implementation of state programs, territorial programs, and draft normative legal acts in the field of protecting children from all forms of violence;

- develops, implements, and monitors the implementation of programs and mechanisms to protect children from all forms of violence in educational institutions;

- organizes and implements programs and measures for the prevention of problems related to the need to protect children in the family, including the upbringing of children in families in difficult life situations, assistance in adaptation during preschool and school education, as well as social adaptation;

- informs state bodies and organizations carrying out activities to protect children from all forms of violence about threats to the life, health or development of the child, facts of violation of his rights, freedoms and legitimate interests;

- takes measures to identify and register children in difficult life situations, who do not attend or regularly miss classes in educational institutions, who need protection and support in the educational process;

- provides psychological, pedagogical, and social support to children who are victims of violence and children at risk of violence against them in mastering educational programs;

- provides psychological and pedagogical support to parents of children who have suffered from violence, as well as children at risk of violence against them, and specialists participating in interagency cooperation;

- approves regulations and internal regulations on the prevention and protection of violence against children in educational institutions, monitors their implementation;

- participates in activities to identify the causes and conditions contributing to the commission of violence against children, and also takes practical measures to eliminate them;

- improves the knowledge and skills of employees of educational institutions in identifying and preventing cases of violence against children;

- carries out the collection, storage, processing, analysis, and use of information on violence against children in educational institutions;

- cooperates with government bodies, citizens' self-government bodies, non-governmental non-profit organizations, and other civil society institutions that carry out or participate in activities related to the protection of children from all forms of violence^[2].

Internal affairs bodies cooperate with state healthcare system management bodies and healthcare institutions, and Article 18 of the law defines their powers in the field of protecting children from all forms of violence.

State healthcare system management bodies and healthcare institutions are obliged:

- participates in the development and implementation of state programs, territorial programs, and draft regulatory legal acts in the field of protecting children from all forms of violence;

- develops proposals for improving legislation on the protection of children from all forms of violence;

- provides medical assistance to children who are victims of violence and children at risk of violence against them, develops methodological recommendations;
- informs the relevant state bodies and organizations about the facts of violence against children and collects medical information necessary for the verification of these facts;
- conducts a medical examination of children who are victims of violence and children at risk of violence against them, determines the severity of the injuries, develops recommendations for organizing a medical examination, taking into account their health status;
- carries out the collection, storage, processing, analysis, and use of data on violence against children;
- interacts with government bodies, citizens' self-government bodies, non-governmental non-profit organizations, and other civil society institutions that carry out or participate in activities related to the protection of children from all forms of [violence\[3\]](#).

Internal affairs bodies cooperate with local executive authorities, and Article 19 of the law grants them authority in the field of protecting children from all forms of violence. Local executive authorities:

- participates in the identification of persons who have committed violence against children or are prone to violence and hooliganism, as well as in conducting preventive measures with them;
- resolves issues of support for children in need of social protection and their families;
- provides information to the competent authorities about children who have suffered from violence and children who are at risk of violence against them;
- takes measures to develop infrastructure for children in mahallas, organize circles of science, culture and creativity, and widely involve children in them;
- takes measures to mobilize local resources to identify cases of violence against children and increase the social activity and responsibility of the population to form intolerance towards all forms of violence against children;
- organizes the provision of assistance in the socio-pedagogical rehabilitation, adaptation, and reintegration of minors under the age of eighteen who have been released from places of deprivation of liberty and returned from specialized educational institutions and republican educational [institutions\[4\]](#).

Internal affairs bodies cooperate with citizens' self-government bodies, non-governmental non-profit organizations, and other civil society institutions, and Article 20 of the law stipulates their participation in activities to protect children from all forms of violence.

Citizens' self-government bodies, non-governmental non-commercial organizations and other civil society institutions:

- participate in the development and implementation of state, territorial, and other programs in the field of protecting children from all forms of violence;
- assists government bodies and organizations in implementing measures to protect children from all forms of violence;
- exercises public control over the implementation of legislation on the protection of children from all forms of violence;
- submits proposals to state bodies and organizations carrying out activities to protect children from all forms of violence on improving legislation and law enforcement practice on the protection of children from all forms of violence;
- conducts research on the protection of children from all forms of violence;

→ interacts with state bodies and organizations carrying out activities to protect children from all forms of violence;

→ develops recommendations for a comprehensive assessment of cases of violence against children, identifying factors that create a threat of violence against children, as well as eliminating its consequences;

→ provides legal, economic, social, psychological, medical, and educational services to children who have suffered from violence, as well as to children at risk of violence against them and their parents (persons replacing their parents);

→ assists government bodies and organizations that carry out activities to protect children from all forms of violence, and also participates in raising public awareness on the protection of children from all forms of [violence](#).^[5]

Article 21 of the Law on the Protection of Children from All Forms of Violence defines the cooperation of state bodies and organizations carrying out activities to protect children from all forms of violence.

State bodies and organizations carrying out activities to protect children from all forms of violence interact in carrying out activities in the field of protecting children from all forms of violence in the following areas:

- mutual informing in compliance with the requirements of confidentiality of information, as well as informing the authorized state body about identified facts of violence against children or about children at risk of violence against them;

- comprehensive assessment of cases of violence against children and their consequences, as well as providing appropriate assistance to victims of violence;

- joint implementation of measures and exchange of experience in the field of prevention, elimination and combating violence against children;

- adoption of interdepartmental joint decisions on the prevention, elimination, and fight against violence against children;

- training and advanced training of specialists carrying out activities in the field of prevention, elimination and combating violence against children;

monitoring compliance with legislation on the protection of children from all forms of violence, development of proposals for improving legislation and law enforcement practice^[6].

In order to prevent harassment and violence against children, prevention inspectors, in accordance with the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 1, 2025, No. 754 "On the Systematization of Government Decisions in the Field of Protection of Public Order, Ensuring Public Safety and Crime Prevention," cooperate with school principals, school psychologists, and inspector-psychologists regarding students who are regularly subjected to harassment and violence within the framework of social prevention.

Prevention inspectors, together with the school principal, school psychologist, and inspector-psychologists assisting within the framework of social prevention, visit the homes of students subjected to constant harassment and violence, study their lifestyle, behavior, and family conditions, take measures to eliminate identified problems, and, if necessary, issue a protection order to students subjected to constant harassment and violence.

Resolution No. 440 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 14, 2025, "On Approving the Regulation on the Procedure for Identifying Cases of Violence Against Children, Assessing the Level of Violence Risk, Developing a Protection Plan, and its Implementation," has been adopted. According to Appendix 1 to this resolution, the Regulation

"On the procedure for identifying cases of violence against children, assessing the level of violence risk, developing a protection plan and its implementation" has been established. This Regulation defines the procedure for identifying cases of violence against children, assessing the level of risk of violence, developing a protection plan, and its implementation.

This regulation stipulates that "Inson" centers and internal affairs bodies shall implement individual measures based on messages in the mass media, the global information network Internet, including social networks.

The basis for the implementation of individual measures to protect children from all forms of violence is:

- appeal of the victim of violence or their legal representative;
- messages from individuals or legal entities;
- direct detection by employees of state bodies and organizations of facts of violence against children or attempts to commit it;
- information in the mass media, the World Wide Web, including social networks;
- materials received from state bodies and other organizations.

If the responsible state bodies and organizations receive an appeal about children who have suffered from violence or are at risk of violence against them, or if facts are established, they shall immediately notify the "Inson" Center and the internal affairs body in the given territory, filling out a notification in the form according to Appendix 2 to these Regulations.

From the moment of receiving information about the fact of violence against a child, "Inson" centers, with the participation of internal affairs bodies, within one day, study the life situation of a child who has suffered from violence, as well as a child who is at risk of violence against them.

It is advisable to divide *subjects directly carrying out* the prevention of harassment and violence against children and *participating subjects*. Direct implementing entities include:

- 1) Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- 2) the Authorized Representative of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the Rights of the Child (Children's Ombudsman);
- 3) National Commission on Children's Issues;
- 4) National Agency for Social Protection under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- 5) Prosecutor's Office;
- 6) Internal Affairs bodies;
- 7) bodies of the National Guard of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- 8) Committee for Family and Women of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- 9) Agency for Youth Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- 10) state administration bodies and educational institutions in the field of education, non-state educational organizations;
- 11) State healthcare system management bodies and healthcare institutions;
- 12) Local executive authorities;
- 13) Citizens' self-government bodies, non-governmental non-profit organizations and other civil society institutions [7].

Cases of violence against children are also being committed by mahalla activists, street leaders, elders, imams, and female religious teachers, who consider child abuse an "internal matter," that is, a family matter. Therefore, it is necessary to increase the role of the public.

Considering the above, we consider it expedient to implement the following proposals and recommendations in order to improve the state of organization of cooperation in the prevention of harassment and violence against children.

Firstly Due to the low level of internal cooperation between the sectoral services of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, 30-40% of cases of violence are not eliminated in a timely manner. A special order of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Approval of the Instruction on the Protection of Children from All Forms of Violence" should be developed and put into practice. This order provides for quarterly joint monitoring and evaluation of the results of sectoral services through KPI. Make it "mandatory" to share information within 24 hours when child abuse is detected.

Secondly, the development of a unified platform "Children's Safety" and the integration into this platform and organization of the work of 13 entities carrying out activities to protect children from all forms of violence. It is necessary to include accounts of those who committed violence and victims of violence on this platform.

Thirdly it is necessary to establish the practice of training and issuing certificates of completion of 40-hour compulsory advanced training courses for entities carrying out activities to protect children from all forms of violence and employees of the mahalla "seven." 40 hours of training in advanced training courses and issuance of a certificate due to the low qualifications of employees of the mahalla law enforcement station.

Fourthly It is necessary to designate one day of the month as "Children's Safety Day" and hold monthly meetings with entities carrying out activities to protect children from all forms of violence in schools and kindergartens together with the mahalla seven, mahalla activists, street leaders, elders, imams and otinoyis to prevent cases of violence.

Fifthly Introduce monthly special television programs on the prevention of child abuse, informing about the facts of child abuse, the measures taken in this case, and news on the protection of children's rights.

Sixthly conducting a "Children's Safety Forum" once a year among entities carrying out activities to protect children from all forms of violence to prevent child abuse.

Seventhly Internal cooperation between sectoral services of internal affairs bodies (IAB) (prevention inspectors, investigative units, public security service, criminal investigation units) is the main pillar of the system of crime prevention. Although Article 13 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ZRU-996 details the powers of the Internal Affairs Bodies to identify, register, and investigate cases of violence against children, in practice, the effectiveness of internal cooperation is low. It is necessary to strengthen the interaction of industry services.

Eighthly, in practice, there are a number of problems in the interaction of sectoral services in the prevention of harassment and violence against children. In particular: The speed of information exchange is low, but in the event of violence, it is necessary to immediately take measures by the relevant subjects. In addition, the absence of an electronic information program that carries out the prevention of harassment and violence against children. Due to the weak internal cooperation in preventing child abuse, 30-40% of cases of violence were not eliminated in a timely manner. It is necessary to develop and implement an electronic information program for the prevention of harassment and violence against children.

Ninthly cooperation of entities fighting against various forms of harassment and violence against children with the citizens' assembly of the mahalla is the most important and

it is necessary to strengthen cooperation. Poor information exchange. Development and implementation of an operational information program.

Itthirdly cooperation with schools and kindergartens is weak (there are no regular meetings between school psychologists and inspectors, weekly meetings of prevention inspectors with school psychologists and inspector psychologists to prevent cases of violence against students in schools and kindergartens. Development of a tripartite regulation "School and kindergarten - Ministry of Internal Affairs - Mahalla" and regular holding of training seminars for employees of the mahalla "seven."

Eleventh A certain degree of reduction in cases of violence is achieved after strengthening the practical cooperation of subjects combating various forms of harassment and violence against children. The lack of role of community institutions - mahalla activists, street leaders, elders, imams, and female religious teachers. Due to the low level of legal knowledge of public activists, it is necessary to organize round tables and seminars with them in the mahalla. It is advisable to establish KPIs indicators among subjects combating various forms of harassment and violence against children. In addition, with these entities 1) exchange of information; 2) conducting joint raids and events; 3) joint development of a defense plan; 4) It is necessary to implement experience sharing activities.

TwelveThird Article 18 of the Law "On Crime Prevention" defines the powers of state healthcare system management bodies and healthcare institutions in the field of crime prevention, and accordingly, state healthcare system management bodies and healthcare institutions should be supplemented with the following sentence: "*When citizens apply to healthcare bodies regarding cases of harassment and violence against children, they are obliged to report this to the Department of Internal Affairs.*"

In conclusion, it should be noted that effective cooperation of internal affairs bodies with other state structures and the public in the prevention of harassment and violence against children will lead to a reduction in the number of victims of various forms of violence. The need for a deep study of international experience and the widespread introduction of digital technologies by subjects fighting against child abuse indicates the need for them. Thus, improving the state of cooperation in the field of protecting children from all forms of violence is the responsibility not only of law enforcement agencies, but also of society as a whole. Its effective organization will become a solid foundation for the safe and healthy development of every child in Uzbekistan.

References:

- [1] Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 24, 2025 No. UP 256 "On Approving the Strategy for the Protection of Children from All Forms of Violence for 2026-2030." <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/7938806> (28.02.2026).
- [2] Bobokhonov A.A. Interaction of law enforcement agencies in maintaining public order and ensuring the safety of citizens // Current issues of maintaining public order and ensuring the safety of citizens: Republican scientific and practical conference. - Тошкент, 2015. - P. 11.
- [3] Latipov B.I. Improving the Interaction of Law Enforcement Agencies and Civil Society Institutions: Doctor of Philosophy in Law. (PhD) dissertation abstract. - T., 2019. - P.17.
- [4] Afanasyev V.A. Organization of the work of the district police inspector. - M., 1990. - P. 38.

- [5] Mukhtorov J.S. Organization and Improvement of Crime Prevention Activities of Prevention Services: Textbook. - T.: Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2012. - P.16.
- [6] Ziyodullayev M.Z. Improving the Management of Support Points of Internal Affairs Bodies: Monograph. - T.: Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2018. - P. 173.
- [7] Ismailov I. Combating Terrorism // Under the Protection of the Law. - 2004. - No. 7. - P. 30.
- [8] Nechevina N.D. Legal Regulation of Citizens' Participation in Ensuring Law and Order in the Modern Period / Edited by A.Z. Glivinsky. - M., 2006. - P. 59;
- Yablokov I.P. Interaction of People's Comrades and the Police. - M., 1977. - P. 27;
- Policeman A.D. Interaction of the police with volunteer militia in the field of public order protection. Administrative and Legal Aspect. - Тошкент, 2021. - P. 63;
- Kolpakov V.K. Interaction of district police inspectors with public formations. - Тошкент, 2020. - P. 35.
- [9] Ziyodullayev M.Z. Improving the Management of Support Points of Internal Affairs Bodies: Monograph. - T.: Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2018. - P. 174.
- [10] Aliullov R.R., Minasov S.G. On Some Aspects of the Application of Management Norms in the Mechanism of Social Management (Issues of Theory and Methodology) // Proceedings of the Academy of Management of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Russia. - M., 2006. - No 1. - P. 36.
- [1] Astapenko P.N. Constitutional and Legal Basis of the Activities of the Police (Military) of the Countries of the European Union and the Russian Federation (Comparative Legal Analysis): Diss....d. of Jurid. Sciences. - M., 2009. 516 s.
- [2] Tarasov I.T. Essay on the Science of Police Law. M.: Printing House of S.P. Yakovleva, 1897. 718 p.
- [3] <https://lex.uz/docs/7219502>. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 996 "On the Protection of Children from All Forms of Violence."
- [4] <https://lex.uz/docs/7219502>. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 996 "On the Protection of Children from All Forms of Violence."
- [5] <https://lex.uz/docs/7219502>. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 996 "On the Protection of Children from All Forms of Violence."
- [6] <https://lex.uz/docs/7219502>. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 3PY 996 "On the Protection of Children from All Forms of Violence."
- [7] <https://lex.uz/docs/7219502>. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 3PY 996 "On the Protection of Children from All Forms of Violence."
- [8] <https://lex.uz/docs/7219502>. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 3PY 996 "On the Protection of Children from All Forms of Violence."
- [1] <https://lex.uz/docs/7219502>. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 3PY 996 "On the Protection of Children from All Forms of Violence."
- [2] <https://lex.uz/docs/7219502>. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 3PY 996 "On the Protection of Children from All Forms of Violence."
- [3] <https://lex.uz/docs/7219502>. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 3PY 996 "On the Protection of Children from All Forms of Violence."

[4] <https://lex.uz/docs/7219502>. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 3PY 996 "On the Protection of Children from All Forms of Violence."

[5] <https://lex.uz/docs/7219502>. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 3PY 996 "On the Protection of Children from All Forms of Violence."

[6] <https://lex.uz/docs/7219502>. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 3PY 996 "On the Protection of Children from All Forms of Violence."

[7] <https://lex.uz/docs/7219502>. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 3PY 996 "On the Protection of Children from All Forms of Violence."

Participating subjects include community activists, street leaders, elders, imams, and female religious teachers.

